

From Flamenco to Bullfighting: Reimagining Spanish Stereotypes in Video Game Narratives

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Abstract

Like films and television series, video games often reproduce racial, cultural, and national stereotypes when depicting different countries, regions, or communities within their narratives. These representations frequently rely on simplified and exaggerated images that are immediately recognizable to global audiences: the French are associated with romance and sophistication, Germans with discipline and militarism, Italians with the mafia, and Spaniards with flamenco, bullfighting, religious fervor, or piracy. Although such stereotypes may appear harmless or even humorous, they contribute to the construction of distorted collective imaginaries that shape how cultures are perceived internationally. In recent years, these issues have generated increasing controversy among players and critics. One of the clearest examples emerged with the release of the remake of Resident Evil 4 in 2023. In the original version, a fictional village located in the Spanish Pyrenees is portrayed as a culturally and technologically underdeveloped society, despite the game being set in a contemporary context. The villagers speak with accents closer to Latin American Spanish than to Peninsular Spanish, wear clothing associated with earlier historical periods, and inhabit an environment that evokes medieval rather than modern Spain. This representation goes beyond the mere use of common stereotypes and instead projects an image of Spain as archaic, isolated, and culturally stagnant. However, Resident Evil 4 is not an isolated case. Across the history of the medium, many video games have associated Spain with a limited set of recurring symbols and themes, including pirates, flamenco dancers, bullfighters, nobility, Catholic iconography, rural villages, and Moorish-inspired architecture. These elements often appear detached from their historical and cultural contexts, functioning instead as instantly recognizable signs of “Spanishness” for international audiences. Against this backdrop, this chapter seeks to identify the major mass-market video games that include references to Spanish culture in order to analyze and classify their representations. The aim is to determine whether the case of Resident Evil 4 reflects a broader pattern of racial and cultural prejudice within the industry, and to examine how Spain and Spanish identity are constructed internationally through video game narratives. More specifically, the study explores which narrative, aesthetic, and audiovisual elements are most commonly used by developers when creating Spanish characters, settings, or storylines. It also examines whether these representations vary according to the nationality of the studios producing them. The results reveal significant differences between games that merely incorporate cultural or tourist references into their environments and those that build highly stereotyped and decontextualized Spanish characters. They also suggest that Japanese developers tend to reproduce a greater number of racial and cultural stereotypes than studios from other regions, particularly when depicting Spain as an exotic, folkloric, or anachronistic setting.

Keywords

Spanish stereotypes - videogames - Resident Evil 4 - character construction - social imaginaries - audiovisual narrative

1. Introduction

As has historically occurred in films, television series, short films, and music videos (Durand, 2004), video games are not exempt from the use of generic racial, national, and cultural stereotypes intended to represent different ethnicities, nationalities, and ideologies. In many cases, these representations rely on simplified symbolic codes that allow audiences to identify a culture quickly, even if the result is reductive or inaccurate.

Several scholars have highlighted how video games reproduce stereotypical national identities. For example, Pitrosso (2019) examined the use of Italian and Italian American stereotypes to represent the mafia in the United States during the first half of the twentieth century, as seen in franchises such as *Mafia* and *Empire of Sin*. Similarly, Chávez (2010) noted the frequent use of Latin American characters as dictators, while Rodríguez Díaz et al. (2008) emphasized the recurring representation of Colombian and Mexican characters as drug traffickers in audiovisual media.

Other games repeatedly employ Russian characters as members of terrorist organizations seeking to impose a new world order, as occurs in *Call of Duty: Modern Warfare*. Likewise, franchises such as *Wolfenstein* continue to reproduce the long-standing association between German identity and Nazism, reinforcing stereotypes about the German people through narratives centered on the extermination of Nazi enemies.

Stereotypes are therefore part of the cultural substratum of societies. They contribute to the construction, reproduction, and reconfiguration of social imaginaries, while also shaping how individuals understand foreign cultures and civilizations. This process is closely linked to interculturality, which is built not only through direct contact but also through the consumption of cultural products such as literature, film, television, and video games (Sanabria Chacón, 2020).

In this sense, video games possess a remarkable capacity to persuade audiences (Bogost, 2010), recreate history (Venegas, 2018), and bring distant realities closer to younger generations. However, as has also happened with cinema and television in the representation of mental illness (Martínez Lucena & Cambria-Badii, 2020), some games move beyond the use of recognizable cultural archetypes and narrative clichés (Canet & Prósper, 2009) to project deeply distorted images of countries, cultures, and citizens.

This phenomenon has contributed to the formation of unrealistic social and symbolic imaginaries based less on historical research and documentation than on the prejudices, assumptions, or lack of cultural knowledge of game developers. Given the growing importance of video games as one of the most influential audiovisual media in the construction of contemporary social imaginaries (Aldegani, 2022), this issue deserves greater scholarly attention, particularly because the existing academic literature on the subject remains limited.

The topic has become especially relevant in recent years following the release of the remake of *Resident Evil 4* in 2023. The original version of the game, developed by Capcom, located its story in a fictional village in the Catalan Pyrenees, in northern Spain. The villagers, with only a few exceptions, spoke with Mexican accents and used Latin American expressions. Moreover, despite the game being set in the early twenty-first century, the community was portrayed as culturally and technologically backward, more closely resembling an eighteenth-century rural society than contemporary Spain.

The villagers lived in homes without electricity, had no access to motor vehicles, and were depicted as almost entirely illiterate. Both the media and gaming communities reacted strongly to this discrepancy between the representation of a real Spanish setting and its fictional portrayal in a major AAA title. The game did not merely use traditional cultural stereotypes; it also introduced racialized elements that, whether through ignorance or prejudice, contributed to creating a social imaginary that was highly detached from reality and potentially offensive in its depiction of Spanish society as primitive and underdeveloped.

Although the 2023 remake removed the Mexican accents from the villagers, it preserved most of the aesthetic and narrative elements that shaped this representation of Spain and its inhabitants. As a result, it continues to reproduce a distorted and unrealistic image of Spanish culture through racial and cultural stereotypes.

Within this context, this chapter seeks to determine whether there is a recurring and traditional vision of Spain in video games, one that corresponds to what Acosta-Riego and Navarrete-Cardero (2017) describe as the romantic tradition of Spain, symbolized through “aesthetically recognizable identity markers” (2017, p. 15). These markers include bullfighting, flamenco, paella, guitars, Catholicism, nobility, and rurality. At the same time, the chapter explores whether video games tend to reproduce a decontextualized and distorted image of Spanish culture, history, and identity—as in the case of Resident Evil 4—or whether this title should instead be understood as an isolated case within the industry.

2. Methodology

The methodological design of this study is based on a review of mainstream video games through a combination of two of the largest international video game databases: IGDB and GameFAQs. Both databases allow searches by genre, year of release, platform, or game type, while also providing technical and descriptive information about each title.

In addition, the study used Google’s advanced search footprint function to identify relevant entries in GameFAQs. By entering the query “site:gamefaqs.gamespot.com intext:spanish stereotype”, it was possible to retrieve GameFAQs pages and user comments containing the terms “Spanish” and “stereotype.” This initial search produced a total of 631 results. Entries unrelated to video games or duplicated records were excluded, leaving a final sample of fourteen video games that include Spanish stereotypes.

The search includes games released up to and including 2022 that project any kind of Spanish cultural or national element in the design and construction of their characters, settings, or audiovisual elements. Since the aim of the study is to examine how Spain is represented from an external perspective, all games developed by Spanish studios were excluded, even if they contained Spanish stereotypes. This criterion was intended to ensure that the analysis focused exclusively on the international image of Spain projected by foreign developers.

No further exclusion criteria were applied regarding the gender of the characters, the genre of the game, the platform, the intended audience, or the year of release.

The following table summarizes the inclusion criteria used in the video game selection process:

Variable	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Type	Mainstream commercial video games	Illegal or unreleased games
Nationality	All nationalities	Spanish-developed games
Genre	All genres	—

Year of publication	Up to and including 2022	—
Platforms	All platforms	—
Elements	Any reference to Spanish culture or nationality	—
Types of representation	Characters, locations, aesthetic elements, or audiovisual elements	Games based on real people, such as athletes, or games that merely reproduce Spanish culture faithfully because they are adaptations of novels or films

Through this methodology, and considering the importance of video games as agents in the creation of social imaginaries (Aldegani, 2022), the results and their comparative analysis make it possible to understand how Spanish identity is represented internationally in video game narratives. The study also identifies the narrative, aesthetic, and audiovisual elements most commonly used by foreign designers when creating Spanish characters, locations, or cultural references.

3. Results

The study identified a total of sixteen video games or video game franchises that incorporate sociocultural elements associated with Spain. The analysis treats both individual games and franchises in the same way when recurring stereotypes and representational patterns appear consistently across multiple installments. Games based directly on real people or sports teams—such as football games featuring licensed clubs, players, kits, or stadiums—were excluded from the sample. Likewise, games that simply reproduce the narrative of an existing novel, such as adaptations of *The Pillars of the Earth*, were not included because their representations derive from the original literary source rather than from developers’ perceptions of Spain. However, *Harry Potter: Quidditch World Cup* was included because, although it is based on the narrative universe created by J. K. Rowling, it functions as a spin-off that expands that universe and introduces new narrative elements, such as the fictional Spanish Quidditch team, which does not exist in the original novels. Finally, all Spanish-developed games were excluded, since the purpose of the study is to identify and analyze the stereotypes about Spain projected by foreign developers. The final sample therefore consists of sixteen works, which are summarized below according to developer, year of release in Europe, genre, and nationality of the studio.

The selected games range chronologically from 1987 to 2011, which suggests a notable decline in the use of explicitly Spanish sociocultural elements in more recent years. Of the sixteen games or franchises analyzed, thirteen are Japanese, two are North American, and one is British.

Although Japan is one of the leading countries in both hardware and software development for video games, it is also the country that most frequently relies on racial and cultural stereotypes when designing characters from other nationalities. Japanese games, in particular, tend to portray Spain through a highly folkloric lens, emphasizing bullfighting, flamenco, aristocracy, Catholicism, or exaggerated notions of passion and violence. Regarding genre, 37.5% of the games belong to the

fighting game genre, while 31.25% are arcade-style games, either sports-based or racing games. The remaining 31.25% include platform games, survival horror titles, graphic adventures, and Japanese role-playing games. Among the most recurrent Spanish stereotypes identified in the sample are bullfighting, flamenco, aristocratic titles, pirates, Catholic iconography, rural settings, and aggressive or excessively passionate personalities. These stereotypes are especially visible in fighting games, where Spanish characters are often represented as matadors, noblemen, or flamboyant duelists.

For example, in *Street Fighter II: The World Warrior*, the Spanish fighter Vega is represented as an aristocratic bullfighter who fights with a mask and claw-like weapon. Similarly, the character of Miguel in *Tekken* embodies the stereotype of the violent and impulsive Spaniard, while games such as *Soulcalibur* and *Fatal Fury 2* reproduce similar associations between Spain and nobility, fencing, or exaggerated masculinity.

The representation of Spain is not limited to characters. In some games, Spanish culture appears mainly through locations or environments. This is the case in *Broken Sword*, where Spain is represented through Catholicism, mystery, medieval architecture, and rural landscapes, or in *Resident Evil 4*, which portrays a fictional Spanish village as technologically backward and culturally archaic.

These findings suggest that video games do not simply reproduce isolated stereotypes, but rather construct a recurring and recognizable image of Spain based on a limited set of cultural references. In most cases, this image is highly decontextualized, emphasizing exoticism, tradition, and backwardness over contemporary Spanish society.

The study highlights several especially revealing cases regarding the use of Spanish cultural stereotypes in video games. One of the earliest examples appears in *Mike Tyson's Punch-Out!!*, a boxing game that features a Spanish fighter named Don Flamenco. Beyond his name—which directly references flamenco dancing—the character holds a red rose in his mouth, another element frequently associated with stereotypical depictions of Spain. He is also portrayed as a classic “Latin lover” figure: vain, handsome, and deeply concerned with his physical appearance. His boxing style resembles flamenco dancing more than actual fighting, and later versions of the character add further stereotypical features, such as a black mustache, long dark hair, and red clothing.

The association between Spain and flamenco appears repeatedly, even in genres unrelated to music or dance. In *Super Sidekicks*, the Spanish football team is described as possessing “the grace of flamenco” and “the organization of Franco.” This reference links Spain directly to the dictatorship of Francisco Franco, suggesting that Spanish football in the early 1990s was still defined by the legacy of Francoism. This association with the Franco regime also appears in other sports games. In *Nintendo World Cup*, one of the Spanish players is named Franco, while in *Street Fighter II: The World Warrior* the Spanish flag originally displayed behind the character Vega was the pre-constitutional flag used during the dictatorship, featuring the Eagle of Saint John. This was later corrected in subsequent versions of the game. In addition to references to Francoism, several games associate Spain with aristocracy and nobility. This is evident in *Broken Sword* and especially in *Ultimate Marvel vs. Capcom 3*, where the design of Magneto bears a striking resemblance to Juan Carlos I. The similarities in posture, clothing, insignia, and royal symbolism were so obvious that the media reported on the resemblance and Capcom publicly apologized before modifying the design in later versions. Another important aspect concerns the representation of Spanish locations and landmarks. The Sagrada Família is one of the most frequently reproduced Spanish monuments in video games. However, in the *Tekken* series, the building is relocated to Plaza de España and its proportions are modified. In addition, a large neon sign reading “Rosa Flamenco” is placed at its base, combining two stereotypical symbols of Spain: roses and flamenco. Some games also merge Spanish culture with elements belonging to other countries. In *Resident Evil 4*, Spanish villagers speak with Mexican accents and use expressions associated with Latin America. Similarly, *Final Fantasy VII*

recreates the Costa del Sol in Málaga through stereotypical imagery, while simultaneously incorporating Caribbean-inspired music and visual elements.

Another recurring stereotype is the portrayal of Spain as culturally and technologically backward. This can already be observed subtly in *Broken Sword* and *Final Fantasy VII*, but it becomes especially evident in *Resident Evil 4*, which represents early twenty-first-century Spain as a society divided between peasants and aristocrats, with little technological development, almost no access to vehicles, and a largely illiterate rural population. The fighting game genre is particularly notable for its repeated use of Spanish stereotypes. In many fighting games, Spanish characters are associated with occupations such as bullfighter, flamenco dancer, pirate, or bandit. In addition to Don Flamenco, examples include Vega from *Street Fighter II: The World Warrior*, who is both a bullfighter and a nobleman; Laurence Blood from *Fatal Fury 2*, another aristocratic bullfighter; Cervantes de León from *Soulcalibur*, who is represented as a pirate; and Miguel Caballero Rojo from *Tekken*, who combines the figure of the outlaw with bullfighting references.

Perhaps the most extreme case is Matador, a villain in *Shin Megami Tensei III: Nocturne*. The character combines the appearance of a matador with pirate imagery, speaks using bullfighting terminology, and embodies a highly exaggerated version of Spanishness. Bullfighting is undoubtedly the most recurrent stereotype in the representation of Spain. In many cases, Spanish characters are literal matadors; in others, they simply wear matador costumes, use bullfighting-inspired attacks, or fight in bullring-like settings. This is also visible outside the fighting genre. In *Harry Potter: Quidditch World Cup*, the fictional Spanish Quidditch team is associated entirely with bullfighting. The team's stadium is a bullring, the players wear matador-inspired outfits, and their animations evoke the movements of bullfighters rather than wizards. Similarly, in *Running Wild*, the Spanish character is literally represented as an anthropomorphic bull wearing bullfighting attire.

Overall, the analysis reveals that Spanish stereotypes in video games tend to revolve around a limited set of recurring elements: flamenco, bullfighting, aristocracy, pirates, Catholicism, backwardness, and excessive passion or violence. These elements are often exaggerated, decontextualized, and detached from contemporary Spanish society.

4. Conclusions

The findings demonstrate that, between 1987 and 2011, a significant number of commercially successful video games and franchises repeatedly relied on racial and cultural stereotypes in the construction of Spanish characters. In most cases, these representations draw on an idealized and folkloric vision of Spain, associated with what *españolada* refers to: a romanticized image of Spain built around flamenco, bullfighting, nobility, passion, and exoticism.

However, some games go beyond this romanticized image and construct portrayals that are far more distorted and detached from contemporary Spanish culture. Across the sample, Spanish characters are frequently designed with extravagant clothing dominated by red tones, roses or carnations, long dark hair, large mustaches, and open shirts. In 56.25% of the cases, characters are directly linked to bullfighting or display visual and narrative traits associated with the world of bullfighting.

Although bullfighting is part of Spanish folklore, it is not representative of Spanish society as a whole. The fact that more than half of the Spanish characters analyzed are matadors or have direct links to bullfighting creates a misleading cultural image. According to official statistics, only a tiny proportion of the Spanish population is connected professionally to bullfighting, making this stereotype highly disproportionate.

Beyond bullfighting, 18.75% of the cases explicitly refer to the Franco regime as a defining feature of Spanish identity, especially in sports games. Other recurring professions associated with Spanish characters include pirates, bandits, aristocrats, and flamenco dancers. In fighting games in

particular, every Spanish fighter analyzed possesses a secondary stereotypical occupation in addition to being a fighter. This contrasts with characters from other nationalities, who are usually defined solely by their role as fighters.

The study also reveals that games with limited narrative depth—especially fighting games—tend to rely more heavily on simplistic stereotypes. This is particularly evident in franchises such as *Street Fighter II: The World Warrior*, *Tekken*, *Soulcalibur*, and *Fatal Fury 2*. Sports games with fictional teams also reproduce these patterns, although to a lesser extent.

Another important finding concerns the representation of Spain as technologically and culturally backward. In 25% of the cases, Spain is depicted as less technologically advanced than the period in which the game is set. The clearest example is *Resident Evil 4*, where Spaniards living in the early twenty-first century are represented as illiterate villagers with a lifestyle closer to the pre-industrial era. The nationality of the developers is also significant. Most of the games that include stereotypical Spanish characters were developed in Japan. With the exception of *Spin Masters*, nearly all Japanese-developed games in the sample present a distorted and highly stereotyped image of Spanish culture and society. This highlights the existence of deeply rooted cultural prejudices and the persistence of a narrow social imaginary of Spain within international game development.

Overall, the most common aesthetic and narrative markers used to represent Spanish characters are, in hierarchical order: bullfighting, flamenco, piracy, roses, nobility, banditry, long black hair, mustaches, and red clothing. By contrast, the case of *Resident Evil 4*—where Spanish villagers are portrayed as illiterate, technologically backward, and speaking with Mexican accents—should be considered an exceptional and particularly extreme case rather than the norm.

Despite these findings, the study also points to a major shift in the last decade. Contemporary games rely far less on racial and cultural stereotypes that may be perceived as offensive or distorted. Several factors appear to explain this change: greater access to information among designers and writers, the influence of social media and user-generated content, the growing importance of cultural consultants and historical research, increased media scrutiny, and the rise of more complex narratives that favor morally ambiguous or antiheroic characters over simplistic national stereotypes.

As a result, future research should explore whether similar changes have occurred in the representation of other nationalities and cultures. It would also be valuable to investigate how players perceive these stereotypes: whether they find them offensive, whether they feel represented by them, and what consequences this shift away from stereotypical portrayals may have for the future of video game narratives.

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